

From Eligibility Rules to Earth Observation Indicators: Assessing the Monitorability of Crop Eco-Schemes in Romania

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Abstract: The 2023–2027 Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) introduces eco-schemes as a key instrument for supporting environmentally beneficial agricultural practices, requiring a transition from control-based verification towards continuous monitoring within the Area Monitoring System (AMS). This study evaluates the monitorability of selected eco-scheme eligibility conditions defined in the Romanian CAP Strategic Plan using Earth Observation (EO) data. The analysis is based on a sample of 2616 arable parcels belonging to 15 holdings and integrates Sentinel-2 time series processed in a Python environment enabling the precise spatial assessment of parcel areas with parcel declarations and 0.5 m very high resolution (VHR) orthoimagery used as reference information. Parcel-level Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) temporal metrics were used to derive indicators for soil cover during the sensitive period, crop diversification and the share of nitrogen-fixing crops, while fallow land was identified through its characteristic temporal signature. The EO-derived results were aggregated at holding level in order to assess compliance with eco-scheme requirements and to classify their level of monitorability. The findings show that vegetation-related conditions can be reliably evaluated using Sentinel-2 time series, while the integration of VHR imagery enables the visual overview of the parcel area. The proposed parcel-based and fully reproducible workflow is compatible with the Geospatial Application (GSA) data model and demonstrates the operational potential of EO for the implementation of eco-schemes within the AMS, supporting a performance-oriented and spatially explicit CAP monitoring framework.

Keywords: Earth observation; Area Monitoring System; CAP eco-schemes; Sentinel-2 time series; parcel-based analysis.

1 Introduction

The 2023–2027 reform of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) introduces a new delivery model that shifts the emphasis from compliance-based controls towards performance, environmental outcomes and continuous monitoring (European Commission 2021, Pe'er et al. 2020). In this context, eco-schemes represent a central instrument for supporting climate- and environment-friendly agricultural practices, while at the same time posing new challenges for their verification, as many of

their eligibility conditions are related to management activities and seasonal dynamics rather than to static land cover. The Area Monitoring System (AMS), based on the systematic use of Copernicus Sentinel data, enables the observation of agricultural parcels throughout the vegetation season and offers the technical framework for the assessment of such practices through Earth Observation (EO) time series (European Commission 2023, Devos et al. 2019). By providing dense and consistent spectral information at parcel level, Sentinel-2 data allow the detection of vegetation development, mowing events, soil cover and crop diversity, which are directly linked to several eco-scheme requirements. However, the operational implementation of AMS for eco-schemes requires a clear methodological translation of the intervention-specific eligibility conditions defined in the CAP Strategic Plan into measurable EO indicators that can be evaluated in an automated and reproducible manner (Kay et al. 2020, d'Andrimont et al. 2020).

In Romania, the CAP Strategic Plan for 2023–2027 introduces several eco-schemes for arable land that require the verification of practices related to soil cover, crop diversification, nitrogen-fixing crops and the allocation of non-productive areas (MADR 2022, MADR 2024). Although these interventions are considered largely monitorable within the AMS, their effective assessment under national agro-ecological conditions has not yet been systematically demonstrated. The high fragmentation of agricultural holdings, the diversity of crop types and the need to evaluate compliance at holding level using parcel-based information create specific methodological challenges. In this context, the integration of multi-temporal Sentinel-2 data with GSA declarations provides the opportunity to derive quantitative indicators directly linked to eco-scheme eligibility conditions and to evaluate their monitorability in an operational framework.

The objective of this study is to assess the monitorability of selected eco-scheme eligibility conditions from the Romanian CAP Strategic Plan using a parcel-based EO approach. Multi-temporal Sentinel-2 data were integrated with GSA parcel declarations to derive indicators for soil cover, crop diversification, nitrogen-fixing crops and non-productive areas and to aggregate them at holding level in line with the AMS. The consistency of the EO-derived results was evaluated against reference data in order to classify the analysed conditions according to their level of

monitorability and to demonstrate a reproducible processing workflow compatible with the national GSA data model.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study area and sample selection

The analysis was carried out on a representative sample of 2616 GSA-declared parcel data belonging to 15 holdings located in different agro-ecological regions of Romania, selected to capture the variability of parcel size, crop structure and grassland management practices relevant for the implementation of eco-schemes under study. The selected parcel size ranges from 0.07 ha to 129.00 ha, with a mean area of 2.50 ha and a median of 1.09 ha, include only arable land and reflect the high fragmentation pattern that characterises Romanian agriculture. The sample was designed to ensure the presence of parcels declared under the eco-schemes analysed in this study, based on the 2025 GSA dataset (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Distribution of selected parcels.

2.2 Data

Multi-temporal Sentinel-2 Level-2A surface reflectance images acquired between 1st January – 31st December 2025 were used to derive parcel-level vegetation indicators. Cloud- and shadow-affected observations were removed using the scene classification layer, and NDVI time series were extracted for each parcel. The GSA 2025 dataset provided the geometry of the declared parcels, the crop type information and the holding identification used for the aggregation of the EO-derived indicators. Very high resolution (VHR) orthoimagery with a spatial resolution of 0.5 m, acquired in 2025, were used as reference data for the visual crop specific identification and delineation of non-productive features.

2.3 Selection of eco-scheme eligibility conditions

The eco-scheme eligibility conditions were analysed in order to identify those that can be assessed using EO data. Only requirements linked to observable biophysical characteristics, such as vegetation dynamics, crop structure or spatial landscape elements, were retained, while administrative criteria and management practices

without a distinct spectral or geometric expression were excluded.

For the eco-scheme on environmentally beneficial practices on arable land (PD-04), three eligibility conditions were considered EO-monitorable:

- 1) soil cover during the most sensitive period of the year (15th June – 15th October), visually evaluated through parcel-level NDVI derived from Sentinel-2 time series on at least 85% of the arable holding area,
- 2) crop diversification, assessed at holding level by identifying distinct crop temporal signatures within the May–September period based on GSA declarations, and
- 3) the minimum share of nitrogen-fixing crops, determined through parcel-based crop classification and aggregation at farm scale.

For the eco-scheme concerning the maintenance of unproductive areas and/or the establishment of new landscape elements on arable land (PD-28) applicable to at least 2% of the arable holding area, the following conditions were selected:

- 4) parcels left fallow,
- 5) other non-productive features such as field margins and the presence of newly established landscape elements.

Due to their small spatial extent, with the exception of fallow land, these elements were delineated using the VHR orthoimagery, which allows the identification of field margins, hedgerows, tree rows, solitary trees and small wetlands within or adjacent to the arable land declared parcels. However, only fallow will be analysed in this study as other non-productive elements were not feasible to be assessed by using Sentinel-2 time series due to its small spatial extent.

All selected conditions were translated into quantitative EO indicators and evaluated at parcel level using GSA geometries as spatial units, ensuring consistency with the operational implementation of the AMS.

2.4 EO processing and compliance assessment

The EO processing was performed at parcel level using the GSA geometries as spatial analysis units. For each parcel, the NDVI temporal series derived from the Sentinel-2 dataset was used to compute metrics presented as a mean NDVI time profile and extracted image chips calendar view. Generated NDVI outputs were used to observe vegetation presence, seasonal development and post-harvest dynamics during the observation period in a so-called expert judgement process (Figure 2). These metrics and visuals were subsequently used to generate quantitative indicators corresponding to the selected eco-scheme eligibility conditions.

Soil cover was assessed by identifying parcels that performed average NDVI values above the defined threshold throughout the sensitive period and by calculating their share within each holding in relation to the total arable area. Crop type discrimination was based on the temporal behaviour of the NDVI signal within the

May–September window and was used to determine the number of distinct crops and the proportional share of the dominant crop at holding level. Nitrogen-fixing crops were identified from their specific temporal signatures and their area was aggregated per holding in order to evaluate the minimum required share.

For PD-28, fallow land was detected from its characteristic low-amplitude temporal profile, while the delineation of other non-productive features was performed through visual interpretation of the VHR imagery using the GSA parcels as spatial reference. The EO-derived areas of fallow and non-productive elements were aggregated at holding level to calculate their total proportion within the arable land.

The consistency of the EO-derived indicators was evaluated for a validation subset using the VHR imagery as reference data. Based on the successful derivation of parcel-level indicators, their aggregation at holding scale and their agreement with the reference information, each analysed eligibility condition was classified according to its level of monitorability.

Figure 2. Example of a parcel with confirmed alfalfa (nitrogen fixing crop).

2.5 Monitorability assessment

Based on the detection results and validation metrics, each eco-scheme requirement was classified into one of the following categories:

- fully monitorable,
- partially monitorable,
- non-monitorable.

This classification was used to evaluate the operational potential of EO-based monitoring for the implementation of eco-schemes within the AMS.

3 Results

3.1 Sentinel-2 temporal signal at parcel level

After cloud and shadow filtering, each parcel retained between 33 and 82 valid Sentinel-2 observations during the 1st January – 31st December period. The resulting NDVI time series provided a continuous temporal signal for all analysed parcels and enabled the separation of vegetated surfaces, bare soil and fallow land based on their distinct temporal behaviour. The parcel-based extraction showed full spatial consistency with the GSA geometries. Representative NDVI temporal profiles are presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Representative examples of NDVI temporal profiles with assessment time window.

3.2 Detection of soil cover (PD-04)

NDVI metrics for soil cover were evaluated only for 15th June – 15th October. Based on the EO-derived indicator, 74% of the analysed arable parcels fulfilled the soil cover condition during the sensitive period. At holding level, 65% of the holdings reached the minimum requirement of 85% covered arable area, while 35% remained below the threshold. In terms of area, compliant parcels represented 82% of the total analysed arable land.

3.3 Crop type discrimination and crop diversification

The EO-derived crop identification (CD) showed an overall agreement of 96% with the GSA declarations at parcel level. The aggregation of parcel information at holding scale allowed the calculation of crop shares and the number of distinct crops per farm. According to these results, 14 of the analysed holdings fulfilled the crop diversification requirement, while 1 was characterised by two dominant crops exceeding the required threshold of 85% (Table 1).

Table 1. Dominant crop shares per holding.

gsa_hol_id	total_area_ha	top1_crop_code	top1_share	top2_crop_code	top2_share	top2_combined_share	CD requirement
Holding 1	56955	108	0.25	201	0.21	0.46	<85%
Holding 2	7178	108	0.35	202	0.28	0.63	<85%
Holding 3	40033	108	0.3	101	0.29	0.59	<85%
Holding 4	50659	108	0.35	101	0.28	0.63	<85%
Holding 5	171629	101	0.37	201	0.24	0.61	<85%
Holding 6	23952	108	0.48	133	0.16	0.64	<85%
Holding 7	49471	202	0.47	101	0.4	0.87	<85%
Holding 8	16661	101	0.45	201	0.36	0.81	<85%
Holding 9	4834	201	0.3	101	0.27	0.57	<85%
Holding 10	136622	108	0.38	101	0.22	0.6	<85%
Holding 11	74802	101	0.32	105	0.22	0.54	<85%
Holding 12	333	101	0.51	202	0.12	0.63	<85%
Holding 13	14985	253	0.29	3017	0.24	0.53	<85%
Holding 14	155	101	0.33				<75%
Holding 15	1864	974	0.44				<75%

Table 2. Summary table of eligibility conditions monitorability.

Eco-scheme	Eligibility condition*	EO-derived indicator	EO data source	Assessment level	Monitorability
PD-04	1)	NDVI temporal metrics above defined threshold during the observation window; share of compliant parcels within holding	Sentinel-2 time series	Parcel -> holding	Fully monitorable
PD-04	2)	Distinct crop temporal signatures; proportional crop share per holding	Sentinel-2 time series + GSA crop declarations	Parcel -> holding	Fully monitorable
PD-04	3)	Identification of nitrogen-fixing crops from NDVI temporal profiles; area share within arable land	Sentinel-2 time series + GSA crop declarations	Parcel -> holding	Fully monitorable
PD-28	4)	Low-amplitude NDVI temporal profile; area share within arable land	Sentinel-2 time series	Parcel -> holding	Fully monitorable
PD-28	5)	Manual delineation of landscape features; area share within arable land	0.5 m VHR orthoimagery	Feature within parcel -> holding	Partially monitorable

*listed in section 2.3

3.4 Detection of nitrogen-fixing crops

Nitrogen-fixing crops were identified at parcel level from their temporal signatures and aggregated at holding scale to calculate their proportional share within the arable land. Only one holding was identified in scope for the assessment. These crops represented 15% of the total analysed arable area, thus achieving the minimum required share of 5%.

3.5 Detection of fallow

Fallow parcels were identified at parcel level from the Sentinel-2 NDVI temporal profiles and showed a high spatial correspondence with the GSA-declared arable land from 1st March – 31st August. In total, 58 of the analysed parcels were assessed as fallow, representing 1.4% of the total arable area and occurring in 13 holdings.

At holding level, the EO-derived fallow areas were aggregated to support the calculation of the non-

productive land share under PD-28, with values ranging between 2.0% and 4.5% of the arable area.

3.6 EO monitorability of the analysed eco-scheme conditions

Based on the EO-derived indicators and the holding-level assessments, the analysed eco-scheme eligibility conditions were classified according to their level of monitorability.

The conditions related to vegetation dynamics under PD-04, namely the presence of soil cover during the sensitive period and the identification of crop types for the assessment of crop diversification, were fully detectable using the Sentinel-2 time series. The share of nitrogen-fixing crops was also derived at parcel level and successfully aggregated at holding scale, allowing the verification of the corresponding requirement.

For PD-28, fallow land was consistently identified from the temporal behaviour of the NDVI signal, providing a continuous spatial representation of its extent. The integration of Sentinel-2 and VHR data allowed the computation of the total non-productive share for each holding and the assessment of compliance with the 2% threshold.

Table 2 summarises the monitorability level of each analysed eligibility condition and the corresponding EO data source. Overall, the results demonstrate that the selected eco-scheme requirements can be evaluated at parcel and holding level using EO-derived metrics within the framework of the Area Monitoring System.

4 Discussion and conclusions

This study evaluated the monitorability of selected eco-scheme eligibility conditions defined in the Romanian CAP Strategic Plan using Sentinel-2 time series and 0.5 m VHR orthoimagery within a parcel-based analytical framework.

The results showed that vegetation-related requirements, such as soil cover during the sensitive period, crop diversification and the share of nitrogen-fixing crops, can be reliably assessed using Sentinel-2 temporal metrics and aggregated at holding level in accordance with GSA geometries. Fallow land was consistently identified from its NDVI temporal signature, while the precise delineation of non-productive landscape elements required very high-resolution imagery.

The integration of high- and very high-resolution EO data enabled the calculation of the total non-productive share and the verification of compliance with the 2% threshold under PD-28. This combined approach extends the range of eco-scheme conditions that can be monitored within the AMS and provides a consistent spatial basis for their operational implementation.

The proposed methodology is fully reproducible in a Python environment and compatible with the GSA data model, which facilitates its integration into national monitoring workflows. By translating eco-scheme requirements into quantitative EO-based indicators, the study contributes to the development of a monitoring

system that supports the environmental performance of the CAP while reducing the need for traditional field controls.

Future work should focus on the extension of the analysis to larger spatial samples, the integration of additional data sources for the detection of management practices, and the automation of landscape element extraction in order to further increase the operational capacity of EO-based eco-scheme monitoring.

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